

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

Medicinal plants with lactogenic effect: A review

Ali Esmail Al-Snafi *

Department of Pharmacology, College of Medicine, University of Thi Qar, Iraq.

GSC Biological and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 2022, 19(02), 114–121

Publication history: Received on 07 April 2022; revised on 09 May 2022; accepted on 11 May 2022

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/gscbps.2022.19.2.0179>

Abstract

Milk production is essential for optimal feeding of infants. The most common lactogenic drugs are dopamine 2 antagonists, oxytocin, recombinant bovine somatotropin (rBST), thyrotropin releasing hormone (TRH) and estrogenic drugs. However, many medicinal plants possess lactogenic effects in humans and animals. The current review focused on medicinal plants with lactogenic effect as natural sources of galactogogues characterized by efficacy and safety.

Keywords: Galactogogues; Lactogenic; Medicinal Plants; Prolactin; Milk Production

1. Introduction

Milk production is essential for optimal feeding of infants with direct effect on growth, development, and health in neonatal period⁽¹⁾.

Galactogogues are substances used to induce, maintain, and increase milk production. Most common drugs used to enhance milk productions were dopamine 2 antagonists (metoclopramide, domperidone, chlorpromazine, sulpiride), oxytocin, recombinant bovine somatotropin (rBST), thyrotropin releasing hormone (TRH) and estrogenic drugs⁽²⁾.

The probable mechanism of action of dopamine 2 antagonists, including binding of antagonist to dopamine 2 receptor in the pituitary, induce prolactin gene expression, increased blood prolactin, increased the synthetic rate of milk protein and stimulate the proliferation of mammary epithelial cells⁽³⁻⁷⁾.

Oxytocin induces contraction of the myoepithelial cells, via a G protein receptor. It also induces exocytosis of milk in mammary epithelial cells by increasing intracellular calcium. Both increase milk production⁽⁸⁻¹⁰⁾.

The recombinant bovine somatotropin (rBST) possessed direct effects on basal metabolic rate and breast parenchyma; the effect on the mammary epithelial cells is mediated by rBST/ST-R complex, which stimulates JAK2/STAT5 pathway, promotes and upregulates IRS/PI3K/(AKT/PKB)/mTOR and Ras/Raf/(MAPK/ERK) pathways which induce cell proliferation and survival and increase milk protein synthesis⁽¹¹⁻¹⁴⁾.

Estrogen possesses D2R inhibition and induces prolactin gene expression in anterior pituitary lactotrophic cells and milk production in mammary epithelial cells^{9,15-19)}.

Lactogenic effect of many plants has been studied and there is evidence that they increased milk production and safe in humans and animals⁽²⁰⁻²³⁾.

*Corresponding author: Ali Esmail Al-Snafi

Department of Pharmacology, College of Medicine, University of Thi Qar, Iraq

2. Medicinal plants with lactogenic effect

2.1. *Allium sativum*

Allium sativum is given to enhance gestation and lactation. A naturally prepared galactagogue mixtures containing garlic increased prolactin level and milk production⁽²⁴⁻²⁵⁾.

2.2. *Arundo donax*

A commercial bolus made of a mixture of several powdered plants including *Arundo donax* improved milk yield in dairy cows, which was attributed to the presence of components reported to be galactagogues⁽²⁶⁻²⁸⁾.

2.3. *Asparagus racemosus*

The milk yield and fat corrected milk yield were found to be significantly higher ($P < 0.05$) in *Asparagus racemosus* supplemented cows. Average milk fat%, SNF%, total solid% and protein% were significantly higher⁽²⁹⁾.

A randomized double-blind clinical trial showed that *Asparagus racemosus* possessed galactagogue effect in lactating mothers. The oral administration of *Asparagus racemosus* led to more than three-fold increase in the prolactin hormone level of the treated subjects as compared to the control group. The primary findings were corroborated by the secondary outcome measures (mothers' weight, babies' weight, subjective satisfaction of mothers and well-being and happiness of babies) and were found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.05$)⁽³⁰⁾.

A multicentric, randomized, double blind, placebo controlled parallel study showed that *Asparagus racemosus* increased serum prolactin levels (primary outcome variable), increased milk production and enhanced weight gain of infant⁽³¹⁾.

2.4. *Coleus amboinicus*

Coleus amboinicus supplementation increased breast milk production without compromising the nutritional quality of the breast milk. Lactating women receiving *Coleus amboinicus* supplementation had a 65% increase in milk volume during the last two weeks of supplementation (from Day 14 to Day 28). The residual effects of *Coleus amboinicus* supplementation were seen even after the supplementation had ended for one month⁽³²⁾.

2.5. *Cyperus rotundus*

The lactogenic property of aqueous extract of *Cyperus rotundus* rhizome was evaluated in rats. Oral administration of 300 and 600mg of the extract induced about 23% and 40% more milk respectively in experimental rats as compared to the control group. Weight gain by pups and mother rats of treated groups were significantly higher following administration of the extract. Protein and carbohydrate content of mammary gland tissue were also significantly more than control group. The extract stimulated the synthesis of prolactin significantly and enhanced lobuloalveolar development with milk secretion⁽³³⁾.

2.6. *Euphorbia hirta*

The powdered plant given to female guinea pigs before puberty, increased the development of the mammary glands and induced secretion⁽³⁵⁻³⁶⁾.

Euphorbia hirta aqueous leaf extract administration increased milk production in lactating rats. At a dose of 200 mg/kg, the extract was significantly increased milk production (40.92%) ($p < 0.0001$). The extract at a dose 200 mg/kg also significantly increased the biosynthesis of prolactin in virgin rats ($P < 0.0001$). Histological study revealed that the extract induced the development of the lobuloalveolar system of the mammary glands⁽³⁷⁾.

2.7. *Falcaria vulgaris*

The effects of *Falcaria vulgaris* on the on the milk production parameters was investigated in female rats. It significantly increased diameter and number of alveoli, prolactin hormone level and prolactin receptor gene expression compared to control group ($p < 0.05$)⁽³⁸⁾.

2.8. *Ficus semicordata*

9.4 kg of fodder eaten per day by buffaloes increased milk yield by 0.36 kg day⁽³⁹⁾.

2.9. *Gossypium species*

Cottonseed feeding enhances the milk production in buffaloes significantly ($P < 0.01$) in comparison to commercial concentrate mixture fed control group animals⁽⁴⁰⁻⁴²⁾.

2.10. *Hibiscus sabdariffa*

The lactogenic effect of ethanolic seed extract of *Hibiscus sabdariffa* was investigated by administering extract and metoclopramide in albino rats. The extracts were administered at varying doses (200, 400, 800 and 1600 mg/kg) for six days orally. The ethanolic seed extract of *Hibiscus sabdariffa* possessed lactogenic effect. It caused significant increase ($p < 0.01$) in serum prolactin levels in a dose dependent manner. The doses of 800 and 1600 mg/kg seemed more effective with serum prolactin levels of 15.74 ± 0.8 and 17 ± 0.6 respectively, compared to control 6.68 ± 0.5 ng/ml⁽⁴³⁻⁴⁴⁾.

2.11. *Lepidium sativum*

The total milk yields for the period of 5 months in the buffaloes received diet supplemented with *Lepidium sativum* seed powder were increased dose dependently⁽⁴⁵⁻⁴⁶⁾.

Lepidium sativum seeds were usually supplemented in the diet of lactating women to increase the milk secretion during post-natal period⁽⁴⁷⁻⁴⁹⁾.

2.12. *Medicago sativa*

Medicago sativa feed increased milk yield, lowered fat, and increased milk protein in dairy cows⁽⁵⁰⁻⁵¹⁾.

2.13. *Moringa oleifera*

Moringa oleifera capsule intake increased milk production by increasing serum prolactin levels. It caused significant increase in the weight of infants⁽⁵²⁻⁵⁵⁾.

2.14. *Musa paradisiaca*

Rats treated with aqueous extract produced higher milk than control and ethanol groups. Aqueous extract increased milk production by 25%, while petroleum ether extract by 18%. The mean of yields produced by the rats during suckling period for aqueous, petroleum ether, ethanol extracts and control were 4.62 ± 2.45 , 4.37 ± 1.93 , 3.65 ± 1.89 and 3.69 ± 1.79 g/pup/day⁽⁵⁶⁾.

2.15. *Nigella sativa*

The galactagogue action of *Nigella sativa* seeds was investigated in mice. Lactating mice were switched onto *Nigella sativa* containing diet from the day of labour and for 15 days. *Nigella sativa* significantly ($P < 0.01$) increased serum prolactin level and the weight of the Litter compared with control group. Breast tissues of lactating mice kept on *Nigella sativa* contain ing diet showed larger acini, thicker epithelia and hyperactivity⁽⁵⁷⁾.

The galactagogue effect of *Nigella sativa* was also studied in female rats. The aqueous (0.5 g/kg) and ethanolic extracts (1 g/kg) increased milk production significantly ($p < 0.001$), producing about 31.3% and 37.6% more milk than control, respectively. The pups gained more weight with the aqueous (0.5 g/kg, $p < 0.01$) and ethanolic extracts (1 g/kg, $p < 0.05$)⁽⁵⁸⁾.

2.16. *Pimpinella anisum*

The effect of aqueous and ethanolic extracts of the seeds on milk production in rats was evaluated by measuring the pups' weights during the suckling period. The aqueous (1 g/kg) and ethanolic extracts (1 g/kg) increased the milk production significantly ($p < 0.001$), with about 68.1% and 81% more milk being produced, respectively. The pups gained weight during the study period with the aqueous (0.5 and 1 g/kg, $p < 0.05$) and ethanolic (0.5 and 1 g/kg, $p < 0.01$) extracts⁽⁵⁹⁾.

2.17. *Phoenix dactylifera*

Date juice increases milk production in 20 breastfeeding mothers. Breast milk production after consuming date palm juice was significantly higher than before consuming ($p < 0.001$)⁽⁶⁰⁾.

Date fruit consumption was beneficial for promoting and increasing breast milk quantity in breastfeeding mothers. Breastfeeding mothers received 10 date fruits/day showed 11% increase in breast milk quantity from baseline to week 2, and a 23% increase from baseline to week 4 ($p < 0.05$)⁽⁶¹⁾.

Suspension of palm fruit at doses of 1 g/kg and 2 g/kg on day 10 and day 22 of breastfeeding increased mothers prolactin significantly compared to the control group. Date consumption dose-dependently increased the insulin-like growth factor (IGF-1), in the mothers and their litters. Malondialdehyde (MDA), as a marker of lipid peroxidation, decreased and glutathione (GSH) increased due to date palm intake⁽⁶²⁾.

The effects of consumption of fenugreek herbal tea or palm dates on breast milk production were investigated in puerperal women. Breast milk volume at 3 days postpartum and percentage weight change were statistically significant either dates or fenugreek groups and control group $p < 0.001$, $p = 0.001$ respectively. On the seventh day, newborns in date's group showed an increase in weight while those in fenugreek or control groups were still below their birth weight ($p = 0.001$)⁽⁶³⁾.

2.18. *Silybum marianum*

Women orally treated for 63 days with *Silybum marianum* standardized extract improve the daily milk production in healthy women 85.94% after delivery, without affecting milk quality. No drop out, nor unwanted effects were reported. Compliance and tolerability were also very good⁽⁶⁴⁾.

2.19. *Teramnus labialis*

The lactogenic activity of methanolic extract of *Teramnus labialis* fruit was investigated in female rats. Oral administration of the extract, dose-dependently increased the milk yield, body weight of pups as well as mother rat, glycogen, and protein content as well as serum prolactin and cortisol level as compared to the control animals⁽⁶⁵⁾.

2.20. *Trigonella foenum-graceum*

Galactagogue mix supplementation containing fenugreek enhanced breast milk production in women and increased infant birth weight gain in early postnatal days^(24, 66).

Maternal galactagogue effect of herbal supplementation herbal tea containing fenugreek significantly enhanced breast milk production in mothers and enhanced fetal weight gain⁽⁶⁷⁻⁶⁸⁾.

Polyherbal formula (contains extract of *Sauropus androgynous*, *Trigonella foenum-graceum* and *Moringa oleifera*) (52.5 and 105 mg/kg/day) significantly increased milk production of lactating rats ($p < 0.05$). The levels of mRNA expression of α -lactalbumin (LALBA) as well as aquaporin (AQP) were significantly upregulated by 105 mg/kg/day of polyherbal formula or 2.7 mg/kg of domperidone administration ($p < 0.0001$). Histopathological analysis of mammary glands shows that alveoli diameter was increase 14.59 and 19.33% at 105 mg/kg of polyherbal formula and 2.7 mg/kg of domperidone treatment, respectively⁽⁶⁹⁾.

The fenugreek supplemented buffaloes diet caused higher daily milk yield compared to control group. The average total milk yield (liters) of lactating buffaloes up to 12 week 28.52% higher in treatment group than the control group, with no significant difference in milk components and also no significant difference in average serum calcium, serum cholesterol, serum total protein, serum albumin and serum globulin concentrations between the groups⁽⁷⁰⁾.

2.21. *Vitis vinifera*

The galactagogue action of the crude phenolic extracts of the grape seed (*Vitis vinifera*) was studied in mice. The crude phenolic extract of *Vitis vinifera* seeds in a dose of significantly increased serum prolactin level in a dose dependent manner, the maximum effect was recorded when the crude phenolic extract used in a dose of 400mg/kg. The weight of the litter of the females treated with 400mg/kg was significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher than those of female of control group. The section of the mammary tissue of the mice treated with crude phenolic extract of *Vitis vinifera* seed showed larger acini, thicker epithelia, and more secretory activity, compared to the mammary tissue of the lactating mice in the control group⁽⁷¹⁾.

2.22. *Zingiber officinale*

Women receive dried ginger for 7 days postpartum have higher milk volume than the placebo group (191.0 ± 71.2 ml/day versus 135.0 ± 61.5 ml/day, $p < 0.01$). The mean serum prolactin levels were similar in both groups. No side effects were recorded in ginger group⁽⁷²⁾.

3. Conclusion

Insufficient milk production by mothers is a real challenge in breast-feeding of infants. There are very few recommended synthetic drugs to increase lactation. There is no enough information for clinicians and mothers to make informed decisions on the efficacy safety and usage of lactogenic herbs. The current review highlighted the medicinal plant with lactogenic effects.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

We would like to thank the college of medicine, University of Thi Qar for support.

References

- [1] Sjolín S, Hofvander Y and Hillervik C. Factors related to early termination of breast feeding: a retrospective study in Sweden. *Acta Paediatrica Scandinavica*, 1977; 66(4): 505–511.
- [2] Tabares FB, Bedoya Jaramillo JV and Ruiz-Cortés ZT. Pharmacological overview of galactogogues. Hindawi Publishing Corporation *Veterinary Medicine International* 2014, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2014/602894>
- [3] Aono T, Aki T, Koike K and Kurachi K. Effect of sulpiride on poor puerperal lactation. *The American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology* 1982; 143(8):927-932.
- [4] Ylikorkala O, Kauppila A, Kivinen S and Viinikka L. Sulpiride improves inadequate lactation. *British Medical Journal*. 1982;285(6337):249–251.
- [5] Alam AS, Imondi AR, Udinsky J and Hagerman LM. Bioavailability of ¹⁴C-sulpiride in dogs. *Archives Internationales de Pharmacodynamie et de Therapie* 1979; 242(1): 4-13.
- [6] Segura J, Borja L and Bakke OM. Pharmacokinetics of sulpiride after oral and intravenous administration in the rat and dog. *Archives Internationales de Pharmacodynamie et de Therapie*. 1976; 223(1): 88-95.
- [7] Wiesel FA, Alfredsson G, Ehrnebo M and Sedvall G. The pharmacokinetics of intravenous and oral sulpiride in healthy human subjects. *European Journal of Clinical Pharmacology*. 1980; 17(5):385-391.
- [8] Gimpl G and Fahrenholz F. The oxytocin receptor system: structure, function, and regulation. *Physiological Reviews*. 2001; 81(2):629-683.
- [9] Renfrew MJ, Lang S and Woolridge M. Oxytocin for promoting successful lactation. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*. 2000; 2: CD000156.
- [10] Lollivier V, Marnet PG, Delpal S, Rainteau D, Achard C, Rabot A and Ollivier-Bousquet M. Oxytocin stimulates secretory processes in lactating rabbit mammary epithelial cells. *Journal of Physiology* 2006; 570(1):125-140.
- [11] Ylikorkala O, Kivinen S and Kauppila A. Oral administration of TRH in puerperal women: effect on insufficient lactation, thyroid hormones and on the responses of TSH and prolactin to intravenous TRH. *Acta Endocrinologica*. 1980; 93(4): 413–418.
- [12] Tashjian Jr AH, Barowsky NJ and Jensen DK. Thyrotropin releasing hormone: direct evidence for stimulation of prolactin production by pituitary cells in culture. *Biochemical and Biophysical Research Communications* 1971;43(3):516–523.
- [13] Freeman ME, Kanyicska B, Lerant A and Nagy G. Prolactin: structure, function, and regulation of secretion. *Physiological Reviews*. 2000; 80(4):1523–1631.
- [14] Mueller GP, Chen HJ and Meites J. In vivo stimulation of prolactin release in the rat by synthetic TRH. *Experimental Biology and Medicine* 1973;144(2): 613–615.

- [15] Cline JM, Soderqvist G, Von Schoultz E, Skoog L and Von Schoultz B. Effects of conjugated estrogens, medroxyprogesterone acetate, and tamoxifen on the mammary glands of macaques. *Breast Cancer Research and Treatment*. 1998;48(3):221-229.
- [16] Molinolo M, Simian S, Vanzulli S et al. Involvement of EGF in medroxyprogesterone acetate [154]-induced mammary gland hyperplasia and its role in MPA-induced mammary tumors in BALB/c mice. *Cancer Letters*. 1998; 126(1): 49-57.
- [17] Guiloff E, Ibarra Polo A, Toscanini C, Mischler TW and Gomez-Rogers C. Effect of contraception on lactation. *The American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*. 1974; 118(1): 42–45.
- [18] Hannon PR, Duggan AK, Serwint JR, Vogelhut JW, Witter F and DeAngelis C. The influence of medroxyprogesterone on the duration of breast-feeding in mothers in an urban community. *Archives of Pediatrics and Adolescent Medicine*.1997;151(1): 490–496.
- [19] Karim M, Ammar R, el-Mahgoub S, el-Ganzoury B, Fikri F and Abdou I. Injected progestogen and lactation. *The British Medical Journal*. 1971; 1(742):200–203.
- [20] Yoshida K, Smith B, Craggs M and Kumar R. Neuroleptic drugs in breast-milk: a study of pharmacokinetics and of possible adverse effects in breast-fed infants. *Psychological Medicine*. 1998; 28(1):81–91.
- [21] Sharif yanov G, Kharrasov RN, and Khaziakhmetov FS. Goat's rue (*Galega officinalis*) in rations for cows. *Zootekhniya*. 1996; 5: 15-16.
- [22] Latvietis J, Drikis J, Auzins V, Trupa A and Kaldmae H. Some types of grass silage used in feeding cows. In: *Proceedings of the Animal Nutrition Conference*, pp. 7–15, Tartu, Estonia, 2002.
- [23] Tomar KS, Singh VP and Yadav RS. Effect of feeding maithy (*Trigonella foenum-graecum*) and chandrasoor (*Lepidium sativum* L.) seeds on milk and blood constituents of Murrah buffaloes. *Indian Journal of Animal Sciences* 1996; 66(11): 1192-1193.
- [24] Srinivas R, Eagappan K and Sasikumar S. The effect of naturally formulated galactogogue mix on breast milk production, prolactin level and short-term catch-up of birth weight in the first week of life. *International Journal of Health Sciences & Research*. 2014;4:242-253.
- [25] Al-Snafi AE. Pharmacological effects of *Allium* species grown in Iraq. An overview. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical and health care Research*2013;1(4):132-147.
- [26] Baig MI and Bhagwat VG. Study the efficacy of Galactin Vet bolus on milk yield in dairy cows. *Vet World* 2009; 2 (4): 140-142.
- [27] Behera PC, Tripathy DP and Parija SC. Shatavari: potentials for galactogogue in dairy cows. *Indian J Trad Knowledge* 2013; 12 (1): 9-17.
- [28] Al-Snafi AE. The constituents and biological effects of *Arundo donax*- A review. *International Journal of Phytopharmacy Research* 2015; 6(1): 34-40.
- [29] Bhinda R, Choudhary JL, Gupta L and Singh S. Effect of Shatavari (*Asparagus racemosus*) supplementation on milk production and its composition in crossbred cows. *International Journal of Livestock Research*. 2020; 10 (7): 157-161.
- [30] Gupta M and Shaw B. A double-blind randomized clinical trial for evaluation of galactogogue activity of *Asparagus racemosus* Willd. *Iran J Pharm Res*. 2011; 10(1):167-172.
- [31] Sharma S, Ramji S, Kumari S and Bapna JS. Randomized controlled trial of *Asparagus racemosus* (Shatavari) as a lactogogue in lactational inadequacy. *Indian Pediatr*. 1996;33(8):675-677.
- [32] Damanik R, Wahlqvist ML and Wattanapenpaiboon N. Lactagogue effects of Torbangun, a Batakese traditional cuisine. *Asia Pac J Clin Nutr*. 2006;15(2):267-274.
- [33] Badgujar SB and Bandivdekar AH. Evaluation of a lactogenic activity of an aqueous extract of *Cyperus rotundus* Linn. *Ethanopharmacology*. 2015;163:39-42.
- [34] Al-Snafi AE. A review on *Cyperus rotundus* a potential medicinal plant. *IOSR Journal of Pharmacy* 2016; 6(7):32-48.
- [35] Blanc P, de Sacqui-Sanners G and Lescure R. Galactogenic properties of plants of the African flora: *Sersalisia djalionensis* and *E. Hirta* *Annales de Biologic Clinique* 1964; 21 (10-12): 829-840.

- [36] Al-Snafi AE. Pharmacology and therapeutic potential of *Euphorbia hirta* (Syn: *Euphorbia pilulifera*) - A review. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2017;7(3): 7-20.
- [37] Koko BK, Konan AB, Kouacou FKA, Djétouan JMK and Amonkan AK. Galactagogue effect of *Euphorbia hirta* (Euphorbiaceae) aqueous leaf extract on milk production in female wistar rats. Journal of Biosciences and Medicines 2019;7:51-65.
- [38] Salahshoor MR, Mohammadi MM and Jalili C. Effect of *Falcaria vulgaris* on milk production parameters in female rats' mammary glands. Journal of Family & Reproductive Health. 2018; 12(4):177-183.
- [39] Al-Snafi AE. Encyclopedia of chemical constituents and pharmacological effects of Iraqi medicinal plants. Rigi Publication. 2015.
- [40] Boodoo AA, Ramjee R, Hulman B, Dolberg F, Rowe JB. Effect of Supplements of balanced concentrates and cottonseed cake on milk production in Mauritian villages. Livestock Research for Rural Development 1990; 2(1):7-14.
- [41] Khaleequr R, Arshiya S and Shafeequr R. *Gossypium herbaceum* Linn: An ethnopharmacological review. Journal of Pharmaceutical and Scientific Innovation 2012; 1(5):1-5.
- [42] Al-Snafi AE. Chemical constituents and pharmacological activities of *Gossypium herbaceum* and *Gossypium hirsutum* - A review. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2018; 8(5):64-80.
- [43] Gaya I, Mohammad O, Suleiman A, Maje M and Adekunle A. Toxicological and lactogenic studies on the seeds of *Hibiscus sabdariffa* Linn (Malvaceae) extract on serum prolactin levels of albino wistar rats. The Internet Journal of Endocrinology 2008; 5(2): 1-6.
- [44] Al-Snafi AE. Pharmacological and therapeutic importance of *Hibiscus sabdariffa*- A review. International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research 2018; 10(3): 451-475.
- [45] Kumar S, Baghel RPS and Khare A. Effect of chandrasoor (*Lepidium sativum*) supplementation on dry matter intake, body weight and milk yield in lactating Murrah buffaloes. Buffalo Bulletin 2011; 30(4):262-266.
- [46] Al-Snafi AE. Chemical constituents and pharmacological effects of *Lepidium sativum*- A review. International Journal of Current Pharmaceutical Research 2019; 11(6):1-10.
- [47] Mukhopadhyay D, Parihar SS, Chauhan JS and Preeti, Joshi SC. Effect of temperature and desiccation on seed viability of *Lepidium sativum* L. New York Science Journal 2010; 3: 34-36.
- [48] Datta PK, Diwakar BT, Viswanatha S, Murthy KN and Naidu KA. Safety evaluation studies on Garden cress (*Lepidium sativum* L.) seeds in wistar rats. International Journal of Applied Research in Natural Products 2011; 4 (1): 37-43.
- [49] Al-Yahya M, Mossa J, Ageel A and Rafatullah S. Pharmacological and safety evaluation studies on *Lepidium sativum* L seeds. Phytomedicine 1994; 1(2): 155-159.
- [50] Beauchemin KA and Rode LM. Compressed baled alfalfa hay for primiparous and multiparous dairy cows. J Dairy Sci 1994;77(4):1003-1012
- [51] Al-Snafi AE, Khadem HS, Al-Saedy HA, Alqahtani AM, El-Saber Batiha G, Jafari-Sales Abolfazl. A review on *Medicago sativa*: A potential medicinal plant. International Journal of Biological and Pharmaceutical Sciences Archive 2021; 1(2):22-33.
- [52] Raguindin PF, Dans LF and King JF. *Moringa oleifera* as a galactagogue. Breastfeeding Med 2014; 9(6):323-324.
- [53] Fungtamasan S and Phupong V. The effect of *Moringa oleifera* capsule in increasing breast milk volume in early postpartum patients: A double-blind, randomized controlled trial. Plos One 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0248950>
- [54] King J, Raguindin PF and Dans LF. *Moringa oleifera* (Malunggay) as a galactagogue for breastfeeding mothers: A systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. The Philippine Journal of Pediatrics 2013; 61(2):34-42.
- [55] Espinosa-Kuo CL. A randomized-controlled trial on the use of malunggay (*Moringa oleifera*) for augmentation of the volume of breast milk among mothers of term infants. Filipino Fam Physician. 2005;43(1):26-33.
- [56] Mahmood A, Omar MN and Ngah N. Galactagogue effects of *Musa paradisiaca* flower extract on lactating rats. Asian Pac J Trop Med 2012; 5(11): 882-886.

- [57] Al-Snafi AE, Wajdy JM and Tayseer Ali Talab. Galactagogue action of *Nigella sativa* seeds. IOSR Journal of Pharmacy 2014; 4(6): 58-61.
- [58] Hossein Hosseinzadeh, Mohsen Tafaghodi, Mojdeh Jalal Mosavi and Elahe Taghiabadi. Effect of aqueous and ethanolic extract of *Nigella sativa* seeds on milk production in rats. Journal of Acupuncture and Meridian Studies. 2013; 6(1):18-13.
- [59] Hosseinzadeh H, Tafaghodi M, Abedzadeh S and Taghiabadi E. Effect of aqueous and ethanolic extracts of *Pimpinella anisum* L. seeds on milk production in rats. J Acupunct Meridian Stud 2014;7(4):211-216.
- [60] Handayani R and Yulaikah S. The effect of date juice consumption on increasing breast milk production in lactating mothers. The 8th International Conference on Public Health Solo, Indonesia, November 17-18, 2021 <https://doi.org/10.26911/AB.Medicine.ICPH.08.2021.44>
- [61] Modepeng T, Pavadhgul P, Bumrungpert A and Kitipichai W. The Effects of date fruit consumption on breast milk quantity and nutritional status of infants. Breastfeed Med. 2021;16(11):909-914.
- [62] Saeed Ebrahimi F, Hemmati M and Malekaneh M. Effects of the date palm fruit (*Phoenix dactylifera* L.) on prolactin, IGF-1, and stress factors in lactating female rats and its impact on their litters' development. Mediterranean Journal of Nutrition and Metabolism 2017;10: 251–258.
- [63] El Sakka A, Salama M and Salama K. The effect of fenugreek herbal tea and palm dates on breast milk production and infant weight. Journal of Pediatric Sciences. 2014; 6: E202.
- [64] Di Pierro F, Callegari A, Carotenuto D, Tapia MM. Clinical efficacy, safety and tolerability of BIO-C (micronized Silymarin) as a galactagogue. Acta Biomed 2008;79(3):205-210.
- [65] Sahoo HB, Bhajji A and Santani DD. Lactogenic activity of *Teramnus labialis* (Linn) fruit with special reference to the estimation of serum prolactin and cortisol level in nursing rats. Indian Journal of Pharmacology. 2016; 48:715-719.
- [66] Ghasemi V, Kheirkhah M and Vahedi M. The effect of herbal tea containing fenugreek seed on the signs of breast milk sufficiency in Iranian girl infants. Iranian Red Crescent Medical Journal. 2015; 17(8): e21848.
- [67] Turkyilmaz C, Onal E, Hirfanoglu IM, Turan O, Koç E, Ergenekon E and Atalay Y. The effect of galactagogue herbal tea on breast milk production and short-term catch-up of birth weight in the first week of life. J Altern Complement Med. 2011;17(2):139-142.
- [68] Reeder C, Legrand A and O'connor-Von SK. The effect of fenugreek on milk production and prolactin levels in mothers of preterm infants. Clinical Lactation. 2013; 4(4):159–165.
- [69] Mustofa, Yuliani FS, Purwono S, Sadewa AH, Damayanti E and Heriyanto DS. Polyherbal formula (ASILACT®) induces Milk production in lactating rats through Upregulation of α -Lactalbumin and aquaporin expression. BMC Complement Med Ther. 2020;20(1):368.
- [70] Kirar M, Ghosh S, Baghel RP and Jain Lakhani GP and Roy B. Effect of fenugreek (Methi) seed supplementation on performance of lactating Murrah buffaloes. Buffalo Bull. 2020;39(2):175-182.
- [71] Al-Snafi AE. Galactagogue action of the crude phenolic extracts of grape seeds (*Vitis vinifera*). International Journal of Biological & Pharmaceutical Research 2015; 6(8): 577-580.
- [72] Paritakul P, Ruangrongmorakot K, Laosooksathit W, Suksamarnwong M and Puapornpong P. The effect of ginger on breast milk volume in the early postpartum period: A randomized, double-blind controlled trial. Breastfeed Med. 2016;11:361-365.